

Effects of Type-4 Wind Turbine on present protection relaying algorithms

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1.- Introduction

Type 4 wind turbines present the advantage of fully decoupling the behavior of the generator from grid disturbances, which helps this wind turbine topology to reach the compliance of international grid codes during grid disturbances. Thus, they are becoming one of the most employed topologies for all new wind turbines installed in the power system, and their penetration is expected to be even increased.

Considering such circumstance, potential problems or limitations of present protection algorithms in the case of high penetration of this type of renewable energies generation sources into the grid have been assessed within Work Package 4 of EU funded MIGRATE- Massive InteGRATION of power Electronic devices Project. To perform the mentioned analysis, an ad-hoc type 4 wind turbine model has been developed in Real-Time Digital Simulator (RTDS) platform, including algorithms for Grid Code accomplishment (Tennet grid code has been implemented in the control system for this study [1]) and independent controls for positive and negative sequence current. The control of the wind turbine is able to limit the negative sequence current even in the case of asymmetrical faults. The objective of developing such detailed RTDS model is to apply high fidelity Hardware In the Loop (HIL) tests in laboratory to real protection relays from different vendors in order to investigate their behaviour.

To analyze present potential relays' limitations, mass tests for three different protection functions (distance, line differential and ground directional overcurrent) [2] are applied in order to compare the behavior of the aforementioned functions in high renewable generation penetration scenarios with that against the same disturbances in a 100%-synchronous generation-scenario.

This paper shows the conclusions and the results obtained in the tests applied to four different vendors (called in this document A, B, C and D).

2. - Test scenarios

For the presented protection behavior study, faults are applied on the benchmark grid shown in Figure 1. The grid model is implemented in RTDS with the objective of making tests in real time:

Figure 1. Benchmark model with CTs remarked [3]

As depicted in Figure 1, Type 4 wind turbine is connected at bus 8, i.e. bus 7 at Transmission network level. Therefore, line 5-7 is chosen as the protected line for the study shown in this paper. Protection relays at bus 7 side of the line 5-7 see the current contribution either from a synchronous generator (G1) or from the Type-4 Wind Turbine (FCWT). The alternative connection of synchronous and renewable generation provide the comparison of the protection behavior under traditional current contribution from synchronous generation (Figure 2) and type-4 wind turbine (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Synchronous generation study line 5-7, bus 7 position. 100% synchronous generation grid

Figure 3. Type-4 Wind turbine generation study line 5-7, bus 7 position. 100% renewable generation grid ¹

Grid configuration shown in Figure 2 is used to obtain the base case and finally validate the settings used for the three protection functions. Once the protection behavior is validated according to the criteria shown in [2], the base case to compare with is defined and tests with type-4 wind turbine with same protection settings can start. The objective of this comparison is to know if present protection criteria and principles are still valid under the increasing penetration of renewable energies.

Based on the benchmark network and types of generators explained above, the variables considered during the tests are²:

- Different fault locations: Faults are applied within zone 1 and zone 2 for distance protection tests, faults inside and outside the protected line are done for line differential protection testing and forward/backward faults are done for ground directional overcurrent function.
- Different pre-fault generation of synchronous and Type-4 Wind Turbine: 40 MW and 200 MW.
- Different types of fault: Single line to ground (SLG), line to line (LL), line to line to ground (LLG) and three phase faults (LLL).
- Solid faults are applied in the case of distance protection tests to avoid well-known classical problems associated to overreach/underreach operation of this function with resistive faults.
- Symmetrical current contribution from Type 4 Wind Turbine even in the case of asymmetrical faults.

3.- Tests applied and results for distance protection

Distance protection is the function that has been found as the most affected due to the high penetration of renewables, as explained below in the present section. Line differential and ground directional overcurrent worked properly during the tests, so they are not treated in this paper.

Synchronous generation scenario

As stated before, settings for distance protection are firstly validated with synchronous generation scenario with solid faults. Once the protection relays provide the expected behavior, faulted phase

¹ Slack bus remains always connected to provide voltage reference to all generator converters

² Further details about test procedure and methodology can be found in [2].

selection and correct tripping times³ both for zone 1 faults and zone 2 for distance protection, the settings are considered correct and constitute the starting point for test with contribution from renewable energies.

Therefore, results obtained for line 5-7 with synchronous generation scenario are:

- Tripping times are correct (less than 45 ms) for faults in zone 1 with:
 - o Generation level of 40 and 170 MW
 - o Type of fault: Single line to ground, line to line, line to line to ground and three phase to ground
- Trip times are correct (less than 440 ms) for faults in zone 2 with:
 - o Generation level of 40 and 170 MW
 - o Type of fault: Single line to ground, line to line, line to line to ground and three phase to ground

Renewable generation scenario

Once the settings are validated for the base case, the 100% renewable generation scenario is tested. Results are presented in this section in terms of statistic results.

Faults are applied both with weak and strong grid conditions (Thevenin equivalent parameters at Slack Bus [2]). Results obtained have been divided into weak and strong grid conditions for 100% renewable scenario shown in Figure 3. Results for the different locations and generation level shown in [2] are sorted by strong and weak grid equivalent in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison between strong and weak grid conditions. All percentage results over the total number of tests. Missed trips= No trip was obtained from protection under fault situation

COMPARISON: WEAK v STRONG GRID		
PROTECTION RELAY	SCENARIO	Missed trip
MANUF. A	100 % RW - STRONG GRID	53.33%
	100 % RW - WEAK GRID	50.83%
MANUF. B	100 % RW - STRONG GRID	38.33%
	100 % RW - WEAK GRID	45.83%
MANUF. C	100 % RW - STRONG GRID	35.00%
	100 % RW - WEAK GRID	28.33%
MANUF. D	100 % RW - STRONG GRID	38.33%
	100 % RW - WEAK GRID	47.50%

According to the results for line 5-7, there are no significant differences between weak and strong grid conditions in terms of unexpected behaviors of protection relays, both in the case of renewable and intermediate scenarios. Therefore, the results obtained for both scenarios can be merged for the following studies. Accordingly, Figure 4 shows the results of failures in tripping decisions for each manufacturer and by type of fault, gathering results for the total number of faults applied, thus merging:

³ According to the settings defined for the relays under test, following common TSO setting criteria

- Both strong and weak grid conditions. As stated before, it does not seem that the strength of the network equivalent makes the protection located at bus 7 position of line 5-7 act different in terms of the number of missed trips.
- Both generation levels of 40 and 200 MW
- All fault locations along the line.

Distance protection algorithm of manufacturer A presents more difficulties with single line to ground faults in first place and line to line faults in second place. Line to line to ground faults are the next more problematic faults in the row and finally the three phase fault.

Distance protection algorithm of manufacturer B has shown more difficulties with line to line and three phase faults than for faults that involves the ground element. Single line to ground and line to line to ground faults are also problematic but less than the other two.

It is very interesting to see that detecting faults involving ground is not a problem for distance protection algorithm of manufacturer C. It shows a clear difference of behavior regarding to the other three vendors. However, this protection relay shows the biggest number of failures in tripping decisions for line to line faults and not negligible missed trips for three phase faults.

Distance protection algorithm of manufacturer D presents a similar behavior than protection relay B, with a worse behavior at line to line and three phase faults and slightly better, but with a non-negligible number of missed trips, for faults involving ground.

Figure 4. Distribution of missed trips between different types of faults for the four different vendors (percentage of missed trips over the total number of faults) for 100% renewables scenario

According to the results observed for these four relays, two main initial conclusions can be drafted:

- Line to line are, in general terms taking into account global results for all protections, the type of faults that present more difficulties from the point of view of the protection relay behavior. At this point, it is important to remark that Type 4 Wind Turbine [4] [5] is designed and set to inject only positive sequence current once the control has acted during the fault even in the case of asymmetrical faults (Figure 5) [6]. The control mode of the generator during asymmetrical faults (negative sequence current equal to zero) has strong impact in protections when there is not zero sequence current.

Figure 5. Full Converter Current Control during faults

- Faults involving ground (single and double phase), in general, present difficulties for protections but less than the isolated double phase fault. In this case, the zero sequence current flowing through the neutral of the transformer contributes in the improvement of protection ability for correct detection of the fault.

Based on these results, oscillographies have been analyzed to know exactly which internal digital signals are being activated in protection relays during the faults. These digital signals provide information to the user about what is happening inside each protection relay.

According to the results obtained and the control strategy of the Type 4 Wind turbine, the most interesting type of fault to analyze in this case was the phase to phase fault isolated from ground as protections have shown the worst behavior for these type of faults. Figure 6 shows each one of the states during a line to line fault. Initially, at the left side of the waveform the current during the pre-fault state can be observed (therefore healthy balanced currents). Once the fault is applied, and during the first instants of the fault (8-15 ms), the converter injects both positive and negative sequence currents. When the control reacts to this fault situation, there is a transition state where there is still a mix of positive and negative sequence currents. During this transition period, control acts and reduces the quantity of negative sequence current. This period takes another 20-30 ms. Finally, after two and a half electric cycles, the whole current provided by the power converter is only composed by positive sequence current. Regarding to the current values observed in the oscillography, peak current values up to three times the nominal value [7] during the first moments after the fault inception can be provided by power electronics during short periods of time. These currents are rapidly damped until the steady state of the fault, where current value is limited to around 1.1 pu.

Figure 6. Currents seen by protection relays during a phase to phase fault isolated from ground

Figure 7 shows the current, voltage and digital signals (without their original names in order to preserve the confidentiality regarding vendors identity) obtained for a line to line fault between phases A and B at 70% of the line with 200 MW generation level coming from the Type 4 Wind Turbine. Here it can be seen that the transition between initial state in the fault (with both positive and negative sequence at the same time) and steady state during the fault (only with positive sequence current even with asymmetrical faults) can be problematic for distance algorithms in terms of:

- Directionality decision: Reverse directionality is determined in the transition state (Figure 7). However, fault is forward. Due to this directionality decision, the forward distance elements cannot be activated and the fault is not cleared in zone 1 times.
- Faulted phase selection: Initially, the presence of both positive and negative sequence current after the fault inception supports the faulted phase selector. However, during the transition period, the faulted phase selector does not operate correctly so that the distance elements cannot be activated to trip the fault within the correct time.
- Impedance measurement is not continuous during the transition period, this will lead to a non-predictable behavior either non-tripping or tripping of the fault (providing that the directionality permission and fault phase selector allow the operation of the distance elements). In any case, zone 1 tripping will normally experience delayed operations due to this variable impedance measurement during the transition period, but incorrect zone 1 operations for faults in zone 2 cannot be discarded.

Figure 7. Protection relay oscillography: (From the top to the bottom of the graph) Current, voltage, impedance and digital signals. LL fault and Type 4 Wind Turbine current contribution

In comparison to the behavior for the same fault with synchronous generation (Figure 8), it can be observed how the case where synchronous generators were feeding the fault the protection relays correctly determine the directionality and detect the phase in fault. Impedance measurement is also much more stable.

Figure 8. Protection relay oscillography: (From the top to the bottom of the graph) Current, voltage, impedance and digital signals. LL fault and Synchronous Generator current contribution

4.-Conclusions of the study and further work

During the study carried out by Working Package 4 of MIGRATE Project, several difficulties have been found for distance protection algorithms with present protection criteria and principles. The highlights of the conclusions obtained are:

- Line to line fault has been found as the most problematic type of fault to be detected for distance protection.
- Ground current, which is present in single line to ground and line to line to ground faults due to the grounding of the transformers, may help the detection of faults.
- The lack of negative sequence current (even during asymmetrical faults) due to the control algorithms implemented on PV generator and Type 4 Wind Turbine has been observed as problematic for distance protection algorithm in terms of:
 - o Directionality declaration
 - o Fault selection
- Type 4 wind turbines present a clearly different current contribution under fault situation in comparison to traditional synchronous generators and must be taken into account from the point of view of possible innovations in protection algorithms or when establishing future requirements for the connection of this kind of generators..

Based on the above described conclusions, future work in this field is proposed to be developed in terms of:

- Improving the fault selection and directionality algorithms during the transient state associated to full converter topologies and control systems that limit the negative sequence current.
- Making a sensitivity analysis about how much negative sequence current would the protection relays need to achieve a significant improvement of their behavior against unbalanced faults in terms of avoiding missed trips. This study shall include time response of the controls and behavior during the transition state.
- Exploring how different time response and control strategies of PE devices, such as grid forming converter controls, would improve the behavior of protection devices.

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Disclaimer

This paper reflects the MIGRATE consortium view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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